

Children Performance Prediction and Plotting Graphs based on Performance

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Abstract— It is a challenging factor that is to effectively analyzing and generating needed information from a large amounts of data. Children data analysis plays a major role in giving an overall view of their performance and helps the institution to make decisions on improving their performance. The significance of this work is to analyze the dataset, which includes student-related characteristics, using method of Linear Regression.

Keywords- Prediction, Machine learning, Linear Regression, performance, dataset, training, Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning algorithms helps a lot in analyzing and predicting student performance for their academic success. This analysis helps in identifying strategies to meet their academic needs. The performance evaluator helps an institution to give the children better education depending on their academic ability. Linear regression has proven to be a powerful tool for predicting student performance in a variety of educational contexts. By analyzing the relationship between academic scores and various factors that may influence them, linear regression models can help identify the most impact student performance. In this seminar paper, it aims the application of linear regression in predicting student performance, with a focus on analyzing the relationship between academic scores and various factors that may impact performance.

II. LITREATURE REVIEW

In recent years, Linear regression has become more popular over recent years as a way to predict the success of students. So many studies have been conducted in the areas of different factors such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, learning experience and previous school performance to examine how each factor is related to student success.

Using machine learning techniques, the work presented by J. Dhillipan et al. [1] tries to create a prediction system for student academic achievement. The study builds its prediction system for students marks from their tenth, twelve and earlier semesters. Decision trees, entropy, and KNN

classifiers are used to evaluate the model. The suggested structure may help students understand their final grade and enhance their academic performance.

Similar study conducted by Ermiyas Birihanu and Feidu Akmel [2] is to create a machine learning- based model for forecasting student performance. The study makes use of a dataset from Wolkite University that contains information about student transcripts and final GPAs. To create the prediction model, the data is pre-processed before being used with machine learning techniques including naïve Bayesian, and Support Vector Machine. The aim of this research is to develop a model that can correctly forecast student academic progress. This research is crucial for identifying underachievers early in the learning process and can guide decision-making for educators and policymakers to enhance the effectiveness of the educational system as a whole.

In a study, Hussein Altabrawee, Osama Ali, and Samir Qaisar[3] discuss utilising machine learning to predict students' performance in a computer science course. The study uses four categorization methods to create a model that can forecast students' academic performance: Artificial Neural Network, Naive Bayes, and Logistic Regression. The student grade books and a survey presented to them were utilized to compile the dataset for the study. According to the study, the classification accuracy and performance were best obtained by the Artificial Neural Network model, whereas the decision tree model found five elements to be crucial in determining how well the students performed.

The study conducted by Tarek Abd El-Hafeez and Ahmed Omar.[4] sought to foresee the challenges students would have when utilizing the e-learning management system. An artificial intelligence-based prediction system was created using ten machine learning algorithms. These algorithms: Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, K-Neighbors Classifier are some of them used in this study. The findings of this study could assist in making pertinent decisions and support the university's efforts to develop technology sustainably. The study determined the key

elements that influence the utilization of e-learning to address students' learning challenges through LMS.

According to research conducted by M. Sitha Ram, V. Srija, V. Bhargav, A. Madhavi, and G. Sai Kumar [5], In this study, the algorithms Logistic Regression and Random Forest are utilized to forecast a student's academic performance. The performance of two algorithms was compared to that of existing algorithms using the confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 ranking. According to the findings report, the forecast made using the Random Forest algorithm is more accurate.

In a different work by Khanyisile Sixhaxa, Ashwini Jadhav, and Ritesh Ajoodha [6], they combined five machine learning models that use a combination of classification and regression classifiers with the Mutual Information method. Gaussian Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbor were the classifiers employed in this investigation.

III. MOTIVATION

Children performance prediction is an essential task in field of education. Traditional performance prediction techniques can take a long time and need specialized knowledge, making it challenging for non-experts to calculate them correctly. With the availability of machine learning algorithms have become popular tools for performance prediction

In recent years, Linear regression is a commonly used statistical technique for predicting the relationship between two variables. By this seminar topic we can calculate each child performance individually and can predict their success.

Every time a lot of student information is entered into a database, it is not adequately organized. Data mining is required to address and resolve these problems. By using the data in the database, we can predict the performance of each student.

The goal of this paper is to forecast student performance using a classification model based on several parameters. It will be beneficial for their betterment.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for children performance prediction using the Linear Regression algorithm involves the following steps:

A. Data Preparation: Collect a large dataset of student that includes academic data. The collected dataset is preprocessed by cleaning it, removing any outliers, and dealing with any missing values.

B. Model Training: Train the linear regression model on the model data. This involves fitting a line to the data that best

represents the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. Independent variables are the previous marks obtained and the dependent variables are the final percentage.

C. Model Evaluation: Once the model has been trained, we evaluate its performance on the testing data. In order to determine the accuracy of a model in relation to this data, it is necessary to calculate metrics like the average square error or coefficient of determination.

D. Model Interpretation: Once the model adequately explains the data, analyze the coefficients to determine how the independent variables and dependent variable are related. How big of an effect the independent factors have on the dependent variables can be determined here.

E. Prediction: Finally, we can use the trained model to make predictions on new data. This can be useful for predicting the final percentage of students and plot their performance graph.

Overall, the methodology for student performance prediction using the Linear Regression algorithm involves collecting a diverse dataset of academic details of students, preprocessing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance, interpreting the model and finally predicting the results.

V. BUILD MODEL

The following procedures are used in conjunction with the linear regression technique to develop a trustworthy and reliable machine learning model for the effective prediction of student performance.

1. Importing Libraries

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import base64
from io import BytesIO
from django.shortcuts import render
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
```

With NumPy, a variety of mathematical operations can be performed on arrays. Strong data structures that enable efficient computations with arrays and matrices are added to Python, and it also provides a large set of sophisticated

mathematical functions that can be used with these arrays and matrices.

Matplotlib makes complex data simpler, making it simpler to spot patterns, spot trends, and find practical insights. It is a Python data visualisation package that is multi-platform. It was primarily developed to mimic the charting features of MATLAB, but it is reliable and simple to use.

Scikit-learn provides a variety of algorithms for tasks such as classification, regression, clustering and dimensionality reduction.

With the Python module Pandas' quick, adaptable, and expressive data structures, working with "relational" or "labelled" data is made easy and natural. Its aims to be the fundamental, high-level building block for implementing Python for real, practical data analysis.

3. Training the Model

```
def predict_pass_percentage(self):
    X = [[self.mark1, self.mark2]]
    reg = LinearRegression().fit(X, [self.passpercentage])
    predicted_passpercentage = reg.predict(X)[0]
    return predicted_passpercentage

def save(self, *args, **kwargs):
    self.passpercentage = self.calculate_pass_percentage()
    self.predicted_passpercentage = self.predict_pass_percentage()
    super().save(*args, **kwargs)
```

4. Calculate the mean squared error and R-squared values for the model

```
print('Mean squared error:', mse)
print('R-squared:', r2)
print('Accuracy:', accuracy)
```

Mean squared error: 0.0
R-squared: 1.0
Accuracy: 99.0

VI. RESULT

2. Performance prediction

```
# Set up the figure
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 6))

# Create a bar plot for mark1
x = np.arange(len(name_list))
ax.bar(x, mark1_list, width=0.05, color='#F6451F', label='Onam exam %')

# Create a bar plot for mark2
ax.bar(x + 0.1, mark2_list, width=0.05, color='#31B817', label='X-mas exam %')

# Create a bar plot for predicted_passpercentage
ax.bar(x + 0.2, predicted_pass_list, width=0.05, color='#F8EB21', label='Predicted Pass %')

# Set the x-ticks to the names of the students
ax.set_xticks(x + 0.1)

# Set the y-label to 'Marks'
ax.set_ylabel('Percentage')

# Add a Legend
ax.legend()

# Save the plot image data to a BytesIO buffer
buffer = BytesIO()
fig.savefig(buffer, format='png')

# Encode the plot image data as a base64 string
plot_data = base64.b64encode(buffer.getvalue()).decode('utf-8')
```


Fig. 1 Plotting the graph of student

Student	Mid-term exam1 percentage	Mid-term exam2 percentage	Pass percentage	Performance
Arsha	50.0 %	80.0 %	63.0 %	Average

Evaluation

Mid-term exam1 total percentage

Mid-term exam2 total percentage

Chance of pass the final exam

Fig. 2 Predicting the final performance grade of student

VII. CONCLUSION

The application of linear regression algorithm method in prediction of children academic performance have high potential and accuracy which helps in predicting accurate results. Based on the previous academic performance results, our approach accurately predicts the final success rate of each child. Overall, the methodology for student performance prediction using the Linear Regression algorithm involves collecting a diverse dataset of academic details of students, preprocessing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance, interpreting the model and finally predicting the results. These processes improve the speed and accuracy of our approach.

This approach has the potential to significantly reduce the time and cost required for calculating arithmetic computations and predicting results. It is easily accessible and can use easily even though users who are not much aware about this. Our experimental findings show that, in terms of accuracy, speed, and efficiency, our method outperforms other cutting-edge approaches. The use of the linear regression algorithm method to predict student academic performance is thus a promising area of research that can help to build more precise and effective ways for predicting

academic achievement, according to the findings of this study.

VIII. REFERENCES

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